

China's Industrialization Trajectories and Its Economic and Environmental Implications

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to examine China's industrial trajectories and its implications on its economic development and environment. In today's international economy, China's rapid industrial expansion is a heated discussion topic in many forums and countries, as it has its own unique economic and political systems. China's industrialization process has been driven by a socialist ideology (socialism with Chinese characteristics) - a social and economic scheme which allows for essential social services and industries to operate cooperatively and publicly in order to achieve equal opportunity and equal recompense for all. China's industrialization process can be divided into two major stages. The first stage is about the industrialization process under the traditional planned economy. The second stage is about the industrialization process after reform and opening up. China's rapid expansion of industrialization has produced an impressive economic growth, but on the other hand it has had severe ramifications for the environment. Like the other developed countries, including the U.S., Japan and the United Kingdom, China followed the "pollute first, control later," approach to its industrialization, in which environmental protection was considered only after considerable economic development was achieved. As a result, its industrialization process has created various forms of environmental problems, such as air pollution, water pollution, and solid waste pollution. As a remedy, China has been using its technological innovation to protect the environment at the same time sustain its industrial trajectory. However, balancing between these two has been a challenge, not only for China but for all countries as well.

Keywords: INDUSTRIALIZATION, SOCIALIST, ECONOMIC GROWTH, ENVIRONMENT, BALANCE

Introduction

In 1984 DENG Xiaoping said: It is impossible to develop any country by closing the door. We tasted the bitterness of closing the door, our ancestors suffered too. It's the long time closing the door that made the country poor, backward, and ignorant.

Industrialization does not mean simply industrial development. The essence of industrialization is a country's economic development and modernization progress, mainly shows the growing per capita income and the transformation of the economic structure from agriculture-oriented to industrial-oriented. Specifically,

industrialization mainly shows by: the industrial activity has an increasing, even leading, share of national income; internal industrial structure in manufacturing upgrades gradually, with its technological content continuing to increase; the labor population proportion in the secondary industry sector shows an increasing trend; urban which is the major carrier of industrial development increases in number and size, and the urbanization rate keeps growing; and while the above indexes keep growing, per capita income of the entire population is increasing (HUANG Qunhui, 2013. China's Industrialization Process: Stage, Feature, and Prospect).

China's industrialization process has been driven by the ideology of socialism. Socialism is - a social and economic scheme which allows for essential social services and industries to operate cooperatively and publicly in order to achieve equal opportunity and equal recompense for all. Socialism as a term also denotes the principle encompassing this system, as well as the political drive stimulated by it. Originally, Socialism was founded within the working class and has been opposed largely of capitalism, which is grounded upon a free-market economy as well as a private ownership. Socialists have promoted nationalization (government control and ownership) of public utilities, basic industries, natural resources, credit and banking institutions. Even though the definitive goal of early socialists was a classless and communist culture, later socialists have increasingly concentrated on social reforms within capitalism (Ernesto Laclau, 1977. *Politics and Ideology in Marxist Theory*).

China's industrialization process can be divided into two major stages. The first stage is about the industrialization process under the traditional planned economy, in which Chinese domestic market liberalized more and opened to international economy. The second stage is about the industrialization process after reform and opening up. In this stage, the Chinese people laid the country's industrial foundation and developed a relatively complete industrial system. Openness and market liberalization are usually complementary; one without the other can seriously limit benefits (HUANG Qunhui, 2013. China's Industrialization Process: Stage, Feature, and Prospect).

China's rapid expansion of industrialization has produced an impressive economic growth, but on the other hand it has had severe ramifications for the natural environment. Like the other developed countries, including the U.S., Japan and the United Kingdom, China followed the "pollute first, control later," approach to its industrialization, in which environmental protection was considered only after considerable economic development was achieved. As a result, its industrialization process has created various forms of environmental problems, such as air pollution, water pollution, and solid waste pollution. As a remedy, China has been using its technological innovation to protect the environment at the same time sustain its industrial trajectory. However, balancing between these two has been a challenge, not only for China but for all countries as well.

China's Industrialization Trajectories

With the enormous success, in recent years, of the Chinese economy, the so-called "Chinese way", "China miracle" or "China model" have become hot spots. Since the industrialization road with Chinese characteristics

is a significant part of the “Chinese road”, a comprehensive scientific understanding of China’s industrialization process is critical to understanding the “Chinese road”. To understand scientifically the industrialization process since the reform and opening up, there are at least three related questions needing to be answered, first, what level has China’s industrialization reached to date, namely what stage is it in today; second, how to describe the past industrialization process, namely what characteristics does it have; third, when will China accomplish industrialization, namely can China smoothly become an industrialized country. Since the reform and opening-up, while China was actively promoting market-oriented reforms, it was also accelerating the industrialization process. In the 21st century, the pace of China’s industrialization has rapidly increased (HUANG Qunhui, 2013. China’s Industrialization Process: Stage, Feature, and Prospect).

Industrialization during Mao Era

The Open-Door policy begun with the treaty port system that commenced in China during the 1840s. For many centuries, China repelled the exertions made by Western traders to infiltrate their country, constraining their activities to the Canton port, also now known as Guangzhou, and exposing them to intense penalties for the violation of Chinese law. After Britain's far-reaching military triumph over China during the First Opium War from 1839 to 1842, the Qing dynasty did not have a choice but to give away large concessions (George Fortier and Yi Wen, 2016. *The Visible Hand: The Role of Government in China’s Long-Awaited Industrial Revolution*). At gun point, China was forced by the British government to open four new harbors to foreign trade. These were Amoy (Xiamen), Foochow (Fuzhou), Ningpo (Ningbo), and Shanghai.

Open ports or treaty ports as a term were scarcely used after the formation of People’s Republic of China, but these harbors still played an important role in various way. During the administration of Chairman Mao, isolationism made open harbor in Chinese mainland less essential. Foreign investment ceased due to the communist rule. Government capitals were basically advanced inland to assure an equilibrium in economic development in the country, and comparatively wealthy open harbor cities were hugely taxed to fund inland region’s economic development. This strategy diminished the economic productivity, and the development rate from 1972 to 1977(Yi Wen 2015. [The Making of an Economic Superpower: Unlocking China's Secret of Rapid Industrialization. St. Louis Fed](#)). This was a half of that of 1952 to 1957. Ports which were still under the overseas regulation nonetheless flourished because their contenders under communist’s regulation became dysfunctional. For instance, ports such as Hong Kong quickly turned into crucial trade hubs.

Industrialization during the Reform and Opening Up

Following the formation of the People’s Republic of China, the industrialization was stagnated by Culture Revolution. Under Deng Xiaoping’s pragmatic guidance, the PRC reversed its long-standing ban on foreign direct investment and foreign loans and began eagerly seeking both. Deng Xiaoping implemented open door policy, different from that of previous. The fundamental points of this policy were to enhance the relationship with capitalist countries, and trade with these countries. In 1978, Deng Xiaoping said: The ultimate politics for us is to do well in economy. Open the door to attract foreign investment.

Deng perceived that if the door was wide open it could shatter the whole economy of the nation at once if the policy is found to be wrong. Instead a pilot projects were selected from the coastal lines and tested against the policy, which was proved to be successful and correct. In April 1979 Deng proposed the establishment of special economic zones. In the year 1979, the central government authorized the establishment of Shenzhen and Zhuhai special economic zone. In the second year, Shantou and Xiamen was added to the list. In February 1984, Deng Xiaoping visited Shenzhen, Zhuhai, Xiamen Special Economic Zone, pointing out that the establishment of special economic zones policy is correct (Vogel, Ezra F, 2013. *Deng Xiaoping and the Transformation of China*, Harvard University Press).

In April 1984, SEZs are extended to the coastal Tianjin, Shanghai and other 14 cities. In February 1985, the Pearl River Delta, Yangtze River Delta, southern triangle of the 61 counties and cities were added for special economic zones, engaging in export-oriented economy, industry and trade integration. Later, the SEZs developed to become development, processing zones, bonded areas, to encourage foreign investment. Foreign investors' capital including overseas Chinese, Hong Kong, Taiwan entered into China. They were given a lot of preferential policies (to implement three-year tax exemption, reduction for two years, some local time Longer, not money or low-cost land, the wage system is free; They can determine their own prices, etc.).

The first phase is to adjust the economic development strategies, the economic structure and develop light industry and the consumer goods industry, so as to raise the level of production and increase people's income, improve their standard of living. The second phase is to develop and improve the standard of living. In 1980's, urban infrastructure construction and renovation (Tianjin, Shanghai with increased revenue) were carried out, to improve the living environment. To continue restructuring, excess manufacturing capacity, a comprehensive reform and opening up is in form.

Since 21st century, economic development is still in the center of government's work, but the meaning changes: concern for the people's livelihood and people-oriented, and focus on resources, environmental protection and social harmony, focus on the well-being index, pay attention to changes in the mode of growth, brand, technology, proposed the establishment of an innovative country and building a socialist rural areas Strategy, requires the development of enterprise and the creation of brands with independent intellectual property rights and technology.

During the sixth five year plan (1981-1986), China more than double its foreign trade, primarily with the West. By the end of 1985 it had borrowed more than \$10 billion from abroad. The decision to seek foreign direct investment (FDI) – absolutely taboo when Mao was alive- was even more remarkable. Although some obstacles remain formidable, the new policy had attracted over \$5 billion of investment by 1985. Deng's most controversial and innovative step was the creation of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) in the 1970s, which were intended not only to attract foreign capital but also to stimulate exports and improve access to modern technologies and management methods (Douglas Zhihua Zeng, 2010. *Building Engines for Growth and Competitiveness in China*).

In 1984 Deng Xiaoping said: It is impossible to develop any country by closing the door. We tasted the bitterness

of closing the door, our ancestors suffered too. It's the long time closing the door that made the country poor, backward, and ignorant. The essence of reform and opening up is to change the long-standing habits and attitudes of people; to change the old system, concepts and ideology, to change people's closed thinking. It also lies in the unifying people's different recognition of the reform and opening up.

The actual results convinced people the importance to attract foreign investment, and recognition of the important concept of a market economy. Market-oriented reform and opening up has been recognized by the whole society. Development has been faster with greater progress. In 1989, Deng said: No Opening-up, No Development. We need to make several Hong Kong ([Maria Tam Wai-chu, 2019. Insights on HK from Deng Xiaoping's speeches](#)).

Compared with those developed countries, the period of China's industrialization is very short but with rapid development, especially after the reform and opening, the speed of China's industrialization is unprecedented in the history of human beings. Because, this is the industrialization of a country with more than 1 billion people, the population of China exceeds the total population of all industrialized countries and regions, and these countries and regions took more than 100 years to complete their industrialization.

This is industrialization with high speed, China's economy maintained a fast growth for 10 years consecutively, and the annual average growth rate from 1978 to 2010 was 9.89%. No other country in the world can maintain such high economic growth speed, even US, Japan and Korea didn't have this speed at the peak of their industrialization ([Liang-Xin Li, 2010. Chinese Economic Outlook](#)). This is an export-oriented industrialization with low costs, products made in China with high quality and low price can be found every corner in the world. This is an imbalanced industrialization, there were huge differences in different regions in China, and they were at the early stage, middle stage and late stage respectively during the same period. In the history of industry, it was rare to see that different stages of industrialization coexisted in one country.

Economic Implications

Big industrial power

Rapid development of industry makes China become a big industrial power. The indicators of China's becoming a big industrial power are four. First, the scale of manufacturing industry ranks first in the world. Second, volume of production and sales of more than 700 kinds of products rank first in the world. Last, the export of manufactured goods accounts for 14.5% of the global trade of manufactured goods, ranking the first in the world. Besides, during the period of the 11th five-year plan for social and economic development for China, the external investment of China's industrial enterprises has reached 229 billion RMB ranking the first in the developing countries ([Yongsheng Zhang, 2006. To Achieve the Goals of China's 11th five-year plan through Reforms](#)).

Rapid economic development has been gained

The industrial development facilitated the rapid economic development, which contributed to the comprehensive national strength of China. China's economy has gained a continuously rapid development.

Especially during the period from 2004 to 2010, China's economy gained a great leap forward; thus it has attained a promoted international status. In addition, China's economic structure has been optimized. The economic development can be showcased in the total amount of the economy but more importantly in the optimization of the economic structure. Since the reform and opening up the proportion of primary industry in GDP decreased from 27.9% in 1978 to 12.12% in 2005, but manufacturing industry and service industry accounted for more than 87% and manufacturing industry maintained at more than 40%. Moreover, proportion of employed population has decreased from 70.5% in the primary industry in 1978 to 44.8% in 2005 (Zuliu Hu and Mohsin S. Khan, 1997. *Why Is China Growing So Fast*).

The growth speed was faster than other countries; the experience of developed countries and emerging countries in industrialization shows that heavy industry-oriented structure is a basic rule in the later stage of industrialization. A new round of heavy industrialization of China started in the later stage of 1990s, by the end of the period of the 11th five-year plan for social and economic development for China, the output of heavy industry accounted for more than 70% of the total industrial output.

People's living standard has been raised up

With industrialization and rapid economic development, people's living standard has been raised up: the Engel coefficient decreased from 57.5% in 1978 to 36% now; GNP per capital increased from 175 US dollars to nearly 6000 US dollars; the average life of people increased from 65 years old to 72 years old; the urbanization rate increased from 17.92% to about 45% (Yao, S.M.; Wang, *Discussion on China's Urbanization Mode in the 21st Century. Sci. Technol. Rev.* 2004, 22, 42–45).

Urbanization

Industrialization is closely related with urbanization, industrialization increases the urban population, and more people choose the urban living way will contribute to the economic development. The annual growth in population was 15 million people (Nicholas Borst, 2012. *Urbanization and Economic Growth in China*).

Environmental Implications

China's rapid expansion of industrialization has produced an impressive increase in the standard of living for hundreds of millions of Chinese citizens, but on the other hand it has had severe ramifications for the natural environment. The process of industrialization is supported by high energy-consumption and high pollution industries like iron, nonferrous metals, coal, Petroleum and petrochemical industries, electricity, construction material, paper-making, cement and construction industries. Thus, various forms of pollution have increased, which has caused widespread environmental and health problems (Peiran Wang and Min Lu, 2015. *ENVIRONMENT POLICIES IN CHINA*).

Like any other country, China has confronted with a dilemma between development and environment protection. How to reconcile this dilemma is a great challenge. Economic development requires rapid industrial

expansion and urbanization; but this often leads to environmental degradation, such as air pollution, solid waste pollution noise pollution, and water pollution (Peiran Wang and Min Lu, 2015. Environment Policies in China). China's environmental pollution and degradation was a side effect that could not be evited since the country has the biggest population and second biggest economy in the world. Similarly as in a number of developed countries, such as the U.S., Japan and the United Kingdom, China adopted the "pollute first, control later," approach to their development. In this system, environmental protection is measured only after significant economic growth was achieved (Dana Biechele-Speziale, 2018. Chinese Environmental Protection Policies and Implementation).

China's environmental issue is also a global concern. Even as the world becomes more and more interconnected within the past century, the issue of environmental protection has equally become more rampant. Environmental protection is becoming an eminent international concern considering that pollution caused in one state eventually trickles into others states by multiples means. It is becoming impossible to separate environmental pollution on a country-by-country basis. The United Nations Environmental Program is at the folcrum of international environmental law, thus influencing national and international environmental protection programs today, as well as the legislation around them.

Air Pollution

Air pollution in China is a serious issue, causing respiratory infections, asthma, lung cancer, and possibly damaging children's development. The enormous health costs of air pollution are well documented by literatures in both health and economics. It is to be the fourth most important health burden in China. In monetized terms, the health cost amount to 1.2 to 3.8% of GDP ([World Bank and State Environmental Protection Administration, 2007, cited in Stoerk, 2018](#)). Air pollution furthermore induces losses in productivity (Stoerk, 2018) and cognitive performance (ibid). According to the latest WHO estimates, air pollution is is the cause of one in eight international deaths, in other words approximateley 7 million deaths each year (WHO, 2014). Air pollution in China, therefore, is a problem that can in principle be solved through the right combination of policies and incentives ([Thomas Stoerk, 2018. Effectiveness and cost of air pollution control in China](#)).

Coal has been the main culprit generating this particulate matter in the degradation of air quality in China. Mostly burned in the north, it provides more than half of China's energy needs. The usage of gasoline and oil as fuel for the sector of transportation is one other fundamental sources of air pollution, particularly considering emissions from cars, motorcycles and jet engines. As the country's industrialization advances, pollution from both the industries and the individual consumer increases because of higher levels of output and consumption ([Peiran Wang and Min Lu, 2015. ENVIRONMENT POLICIES IN CHINA](#)).

Water Pollution

China's water pollution problem is another big environmental issue. According to an official report by the Ministry of Water Resources in 2012, up to about 40 percent of China's rivers were extremely polluted and about 20 percent were very polluted such that the quality of the water was rated gravely lethal just to come into contact with. According to report assessments, there are a huge number of petrochemical plants along the Yellow Rivers and the Yangtze. Polluted wastewater are potentially leaching into, or even worse simply discarded into China's rivers from factories (Elizabeth 2013, cited in Peiran Wang and Min Lu, 2015. *Environment Policies In China*). There have been enormous measures of deposits of toxic and organic households, agriculture and industry waste.

Proportion of Water Quality Grade of Provincial Boundary Water Sections Nationwide in 2017.

Source: Ministry of Environmental Protection, the People's Republic of China.

Grade I or II indicates the water could be used in the first-class protection zones for drinking water sources, habitats of rare aquatic species, fish and shrimp spawning grounds and feeding grounds of young fish and fish larvae. Grade III refers to water that could be used in the second-class protection zones for drinking water sources, fish and shrimp's overwintering ground, migration channels, aquaculture areas and swimming sites. Grade IV indicates the water is only suitable for industrial use and other purposes such as amusement that do not include the fluid getting into contact with the skin. Grade V indicates the water is only suitable for agriculture and landscape. Water failing to meet Grade V standard hardly has any function except regulating local climate ([Ministry of Environmental Protection Report 2017, the People's Republic of China](#)).

Soil Contamination

Soil contamination threatens agricultural safety in some parts of China. In 2011 an investigation of soil conducted by the China National Environmental Monitoring Centre (CNEMC) on around 284 factories, mines and enterprises showed that the quantity of clean land was 68.1%, mildly polluted land (13.1%), moderately polluted land (3.3%) and heavily polluted land (13.5%). The top six pollutants were cadmium, arsenic, nickel, copper, mercury and chromium (Peiran Wang and Min Lu, 2015. ENVIRONMENT POLICIES IN CHINA). Especially in the last two decades, major transformations have been made in China's environmental policy, from priority placed on economic development to equal emphasis placed on both environmental protection and economic development. Several laws and plans have been enacted by the Chinese government to curb pollution. Economic development and a sustainable environment are regarded as the key components of the development strategy of the state. In 1979 China passed the first environmental protection law 1979 ([Zhilin Mu 1,*](#), [Shuchun Bu 2 and Bing Xue 3,4,*](#), 2014), which is the cardinal law for environmental protection in China ([retrieved from http://www.china.org.cn/english/environment/34356.htm](http://www.china.org.cn/english/environment/34356.htm)).

The law has recognized the fundamental principle for a synchronized improvement between social progress, economic construction, and environmental protection, and defined the government's privileges and responsibilities at all levels, as regards environmental protection, and for all units and individuals. Since the passing of this regulation in China, the country's environmental law has extended to inculcate about thirty major bills in conjunction with numerous State Council standards and protocols. The most important regulations include the Law on the Prevention and Control of Atmospheric Pollution, Environmental Impact Assessment Law, and the Law on the Prevention and Control of Water Pollution, with other regulations ranging from desertification prevention to clean energy production and to forestry

Conclusion and recommendations

Within a period of about sixty years, most especially within the last thirty years after China's reform and opening up, the country has basically been metamorphosed into a modern industrialized state from the once traditional agricultural nation. There is no doubt that China's industrialization has improved the living standards of millions of Chinese. In spite of this great success, the industrialization process in China has also given rise

to enormous problems, including social inequality, high levels of energy use from extensive industrialization and the degradation of the environment such as air pollution, worsening water quality as well as land contamination.

As China battles a serious conflict with sustaining its industrialization and environmental decline, industrial expansion has historically prevailed at the expense of the environment. To strike a balance between monetary and environmental profits such that neither succeeds at the direct expense of the other remains a big challenge for China. This coexistence of industrialization and environmental protection are both very much dependent on one another, which deserve proper attention and handling.

The regulation and deterrence of ecological pollution and environmental destruction and the rational exploitation and the use of natural resources are of crucial significance to China's overall industrialization expansion and long-term economic development. For this reason, the “pollute first, control later,” approach should be reversed. Industrialization policies and benefits should incorporate environmental management policies. Moreover, causers of pollution should be held responsible for treating it. The progress of environmental science and technology should be accelerated. In addition, to enhance the whole nation's awareness of the environment, environmental publicity and education should be considered on its large scale. Last but not list, China should promote international cooperation in the field of environmental protection. Furthermore, it should expand exchanges and cooperation concerning the environment and development with other countries and international organizations.

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